

Qualitative coding of temporally, spatially, and contextually situated data in wartime diaries

An exploratory methodological report (MAXQDA pilot study)

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1. Introduction

This report addresses methodological challenges of analyzing wartime diaries as qualitative data. Published diaries resist standardization: they're written in multiple languages, across diverse regions, with non-linear temporal structures and highly contextual vocabularies. How do you systematically code such material?

I demonstrate solutions in MAXQDA: (i) defining units of analysis within heterogeneous literary sources, (ii) handling temporal and spatial data across non-linear narratives, (iii) managing multilingual vocabularies, and (iv) designing coding systems that capture both metadata and analytical themes. The report pays particular attention to temporal layering, shifting spatial references, and using MAXQDA tools to trace co-occurrence and ambivalence within diary fragments.

Empirical illustration draws on three Ukrainian wartime diaries (published since Russia's 2022 full-scale invasion) authored by intellectuals from three regions: Mariupol, Kharkiv, and Kyiv. The analysis identifies patterns of "ambivalent normality" - how everyday life paradoxically continues under war conditions. These findings illustrate the methodological approach rather than make definitive empirical claims.

Context: This pilot study was prepared within a doctoral-level MAXQDA course at the Graduate School for Social Research, Polish Academy of Sciences, as part of broader doctoral research developing a social phenomenological theory of "the Stayer" - those who remain in place while their world transforms around them (<http://thestayer.org>).

2. Theoretical concept and its operationalisation

This project operationalises the central theoretical concept of my doctoral dissertation – **the Stayer**. Engaging with one of sociology's most enduring issues – estrangement and alienation – it challenges prevailing approaches to the condition of estrangement as the detachment of an individual (or small group) from their community and social world around. Classical sociological perspectives link estrangement to movement and arrival between stable social worlds, while critical and existential traditions address different forms of detachment and isolation. What remains unaccounted for is estrangement without movement – where an entire community experiences their homeworld turning alien while staying in place.

In response to this theoretical gap, my study introduces the sociological figure of the Stayer – one who remains physically in place, still connected to their community, while their social world undergoes radical change – for example, in the case of wars, occupations, pandemics, or disasters. The Stayer, thus, embodies the ambivalent condition of being grounded in homeland and community while simultaneously estranged from the transformed world.

To operationalize this concept, I introduce criteria that trigger the staying as a specific type of lived experience: (1) the Stayer stays in place while their world transforms radically (*unlike migrants or refugees*), (2) they consciously experience the disruption and have memory of life before (*unlike children born in the conflict zones*), (3) they stay by decision, not just constraint (*unlike those in besieged cities*), (4) the disruption persists over time (*not the experience of the first shock*), (5) they are not detached or estranged from their group, (6) they are ambivalently estranged from their world – feeling both embedded and not accepting from its transformed state (*e.g. those who embrace occupation cease to be Stayers*).

Among the many possible real-world instantiations that meet these criteria, this study focuses on the **target group** of intellectuals – a distinct group marked by a high level of public engagement and forming recognisable professional communities. In wartime Ukraine, many intellectuals – scholars, writers, journalists, and artists – reframed their activities around war and immersed themselves in volunteering and organising cultural events in the most vulnerable regions. Dozens of them continue to write about their experiences on social media, in newspaper columns, in collections of essays, and in personal diaries, which often become published as books.

These published diaries, memoirs, and essays, written after February 24, 2022, in both single-authored and collective books, constitute the body of **empirical sources** for my study. From the broad body of published diaries, I focus on texts that meet the above criteria of the staying and written by Ukrainian intellectuals affiliated with PEN Ukraine – a well-established and publicly active organization whose members are frequently involved in collaborative wartime projects and actively publish individual diaries and edited volumes of wartime diaries and essay collections.

Within this subcorpus, in my pilot study, I analyse three distinct cases, each represented by a published diary or a fragment authored by a PEN-affiliated intellectual. My **sample**, thus, includes three diaries from three Ukrainian cities that were differently exposed to wartime conditions: *Mariupol* (which was besieged and subjected to carpet bombing during the first months of 2022), *Kharkiv* (a frontline city under sustained missile attacks), and *Kyiv* (a relatively protected city, yet one under constant threat and targeted in mass-scale strikes).

This conceptual and empirical groundwork enables the following formulation of the **research question**: How do Ukrainian intellectuals who remain in place during full-scale Russia's war in Ukraine narrate their experience of *the staying*, and how does this narration evolve over time?

While I expect to identify multiple traits that emerge within the condition of the staying and shape the Stayer as a specific type of experience and subjectivity, **the question this pilot study asks** is: How does wartime experience transform the boundaries between what is considered normal and abnormal? How do everyday practices continue, adapt, or shift in meaning under prolonged conditions of war? What remains unchanged – and what begins to feel routine, even when it once seemed unthinkable?

In terms of qualitative data analysis, this question takes the following form: How do themes related to continuity of pre-war 'normal life' and the normalization of the previously abnormal co-occur and are experientially entangled within the same or nearby diary segments – not simply mentioned side by side, but narratively or reflectively intertwined (e.g. "*I was drinking coffee when the air raid siren started*").

This data selection and research question define specific methodological challenges I discuss in the following sections. By addressing these challenges, I develop a research design that encompasses the structure of documents, variables, and codes, which can handle the complexities of a theoretically grounded, multilingual, literature-based, *interpretive research* project, exemplified by my doctoral work.

3. Data analysis challenges and Research design in MAXQDA

3.1. Units of Analysis, Document Structure, and Variables

Challenge. The first challenge one encounters when designing a qualitative research project based on literary texts lies in defining appropriate units of analysis. Unlike more unified sources, such as interviews, these texts are not produced in response to standardised prompts and are thus thematically and structurally heterogeneous. Some volumes are single-authored diaries with a clear temporal progression; others are collective anthologies of essays that span different chronological periods and locations. Even within a single-authored volume, entries can address different aspects: some are relevant to our study (*in my case, descriptions of staying*

in war-torn cities), while others are not (*e.g. stories about evacuation or exile*). This raises a methodological dilemma: should the unit of analysis (or a Document, in MAXQDA's terms) be the entire book, individual chapters or entries, or smaller narrative segments?

It was not possible to break volumes down by cities or regions – again due to non-standardised writing throughout the sources. Authors often mention several regions in one diary entry, and these mentions frequently overlap. *For example, an author can describe staying in a shelter during an air alert in Kyiv and messaging with their family in the attacked city of Kharkiv.* For the same reason, it was also not possible to break volumes down by dates of the entries: the approaches varied too strongly across different volumes and often even within the same diary. Some volumes evolved through a non-linear trajectory, using various and flexible time intervals, and many did not contain explicit dating at all.

Finally, the diverse and non-standardised corpus of sources also appeared minimally suitable for using variables. Although each document was clearly related to one author, as in the case of interviews or surveys, each author might contribute to several volumes. It would have been logical to assign each document an “Author” variable – if MAXQDA's variable system were database-driven. Surprisingly, it is not. Variables are not relational entities here; they are stored only as direct entries per document. As a result, it is impossible to create an author-level metadata profile and associate it across multiple texts. Consequently, in cases of one-to-many relations between documents and authors, each document would redundantly store variables such as gender and profession. In other words, while variables may work well in standardised designs, such as interview-based studies, where one document corresponds to one person, they become impractical for the more complex data structures.

Solution. Given this, I have chosen the criteria of authorship to separate units of analysis. The MAXQDA *Document* is, thus, a narrative *fragment* authored by a single author or (in rare hypothetical cases) a group of authors. In the case of single-authored diaries, the entire book may be treated as a single text, with non-relevant parts (*e.g., refugee experiences*) excluded during preprocessing. For collective volumes, the document is a single chapter or essay authored by an individual author. The documents can then be organized in *document groups* or *sets* – I am currently leaning towards using document groups and reserving sets for further analytical purposes.

This approach is efficient if the same author contributed to several collected volumes, and also if we consider supplementing published diaries with later evidence, such as social media posts by the same authors or subsequent interviews with them. In this case, we may easily differentiate between types of documents using document variables (*e.g. entire book, fragment, interview, social media post, etc.*).

Folder/Document	Count
Documents	59
Kari	23
Kari - FB 2025--03-23	0
Карі 2022 - Життя посеред життя OCR	23
Sukhorukova	11
Sukhorukova - Interview	0
Сухорукова 2023 - #Маріуполь #Надія OCR	11
Skalietska	8
Skalietska 2022 - Part about Ukraine OCR	8

Figure 1. Document structure in MAXQDA.

To compensate for MAXQDA’s lack of an integrated metadata structure, I created a supplementary author-level table using *Coda.io*, where relevant biographical and contextual information is stored for future use.

Check daily	Name	Narrator's type	Gender	Narrator's URL	Notes
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ройз Світлана	Psychologist	▼	▼	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sasha Boole & ...	Artists	▼	▼	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Шаповал Юрій	Artists	▼	▼	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<Other bloggers>	Bloggers	▼	▼	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<Other children>	Children	▼	▼	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Skalietska Yeva	Children	▼	▼	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Amelina Victoria	Journalists	▼	▼	

Figure 2. Extended Authors table in Coda.io.

3.2. Temporal and Spatial Data

Challenge. Another major challenge in diary-based research is how to handle their time-related structure. As any narrations, diaries and (auto)biographical texts are inherently temporal: they reconstruct lived experience as it unfolds over time. And unless we retrospective use of pre-existing diaries and a more prospective or solicited use of diary writing in research.

The task of dealing with this temporality in diaries may seem easier compared to other texts, as their temporal structure is expected to be more explicit and straightforward. This works well in *solicited diary studies*, in which participants are provided with instructions how to document their experience. This may also work in *retrospective diary research* with diaries of ordinary people who are more likely to follow simple chronological trajectory. This task becomes more complex when working with diaries written by professional writers, which often deviate from strictly chronological formats. Even texts originally written as dated diaries may be restructured for publication – edited into literary essays, grouped thematically, or reshaped into non-linear narratives. Some diarists use clear date-stamped entries while in texts by others temporal

references appear only occasionally; some follow a more novelistic form, and others intersperse the narration with memories or theorizing. These non-linearities are especially problematic when a researcher works with multiple diaries, attempting to trace common processes or build periodizations. This makes it difficult to define consistent temporal units across the corpus or to align them with thematic data.

A number of methodological questions arise in this regard. What should carry temporal information: variables or codes? Or should the documents themselves be broken up into date-stamped segments that reflect the internal chronology of narration? If we use codes – how detailed should they be? Should each date receive its own code? How can these segments be meaningfully consolidated at later stages of analysis?

Solution. To address these issues, I created a set of **temporal technical codes** to be assigned to large segments of text – up to entire chapters or even documents if they described one chronological interval. In the pilot study, I used technical codes to capture two types of temporal data: (i) objective time – basic chronology, such as calendar dates; (ii) significant political or military events, such attacks and counterattacks, crucial political decisions and negotiations. These codes remained emergent throughout the study and were allowed to consolidate organically – for example, merging in months and then in broader stages of war.

In parallel, the **analytical code system** included an open, emergent set of codes that captured *subjective temporality* – such as perceived acceleration or stagnation of time, temporal disorientation, or focus on past or future. Soon, a *phenomenological periodization of the staying* began to emerge, with phases from initial shock and survival to informed adaptation and further to a state where war became an awful yet routinized background.

In addition to temporal metadata, I used a parallel set of **spatial technical codes** to mark spatial contexts – such as such as besieged cities, frontline zones, or relatively protected regions. Since a single document (i.e., a narrative text authored by one person or group) may refer to multiple locations, spatial metadata cannot always be assigned at the document level through variables. In contrast, technical codes allow for granular, segment-level spatial markup. Among other things, this enables analysis of how different regional experiences are represented within and across texts.

Together, these spatial and temporal code sets constitute a flexible metadata layer that supports subsequent thematic analysis.

Figure 3. Code book: Technical and Analytical Codes.

3.3. Multicontextuality and Multilinguality

Challenge. The specificity of this research lies in its attempt to trace subjective experiences and interpret subtle transformations in how the world is lived and understood deeply embedded in language and context. An attempt to reach these experiences through published diaries is challenging, as their structure and vocabulary are highly diverse – unlike more standardized sources, such as interviews (even semi-structured) or diaries in solicited diary analysis. On contrast, published diaries are authored independently by people from diverse regions and cultural backgrounds and are thus highly *contextual*.

Their vocabularies differ significantly due to linguistic variation between regions of Ukraine. Furthermore, when authors are mostly professional writers and scholars, their language tends to be more metaphorical, abstract, and complex than that of ordinary people. Next, wartime necessarily triggers an explosion of neologisms and linguistic transformations (*refs). Many common words change their meanings and carry meanings that are highly context-specific and often unrecognizable for someone beyond the context.

This diversity may be neglected or considered secondary when we address data sources in a realistic or positivist way – as valid testimonies that give us access to ‘real-world’ facts or

events and where unique narrative style and voice of respondents are rather ‘noise’ to reduce. But it becomes central when we address data sources as narratives which are not expected to be just pathways to facts but are of interest as a self-sufficient fabric of meanings.

In addition, such non-standardized body of data sources is very likely to be *multilingual*. While early war diaries were written preliminary in Ukrainian, authors from Eastern regions also used Russian, and later diaries are often written in English with a view for international audience.

This diversity complicates the process of thematic analysis and coding. It sets exceptionally high requirements for the researcher, who must not only possess linguistic fluency in all languages used across the dataset but also be deeply linguistically, culturally, and contextually embedded both into stable pre-war lifeworld and wartime atmosphere. For example, one diary in my sample mentions a visit to *Musafir*, a well-known café in Kyiv. To an outsider, this may appear as a neutral location, but for those familiar with the city’s cultural life, on one hand, and the situation of the first days of full-scale war, on another, this moment signals something profound: the return of normality after days of fear and uncertainty. In other words, the researcher must be a genuine insider – someone capable of grasping nuanced meanings, regionally specific expressions, and subtle shifts in vocabulary shaped by both local diversity and wartime transformations.

For these reasons, such research is difficult to automate using tools like AI-based text analysis or automatic coding in MAXQDA. It is also challenging to delegate parts of work to a research team unless every team member meets the same demanding criteria of linguistic proficiency and contextual embeddedness.

Solution. To address this challenge, I preceded thematic coding with an exploratory stage – simple word-level analysis with MaxDictio tools. I populated thematic dictionaries only with words from source documents, which I retrieved via *word frequency analysis for each diary in the study* and thoroughly looked them through while manually saving all terms that seemed war-related into document-specific dictionary (with naturally evolving subcategories). This is where personal embeddedness is crucial: dozens of recently common everyday words turned out to fall into these dictionaries due to their new wartime connotations: *wall*, *basement*, *corridor*, *elevator shaft* – clear references to places to hide behind, *loud* – marker of explosions, *wave* – explosion wave, *torn off* – about legs or hands, *to fly* – about rockets or drones, *to blow out* – about windows under explosions, *most of the words denoting sounds* – about missiles, *most of the verbs denoting approaching* – about missiles, etcetera.

Although rough, this preliminary analysis was definitely more precise and adequate comparing to applying the same standardized word list to all diaries. On contrast, I addressed each diary with its own authentic vocabulary, avoiding forced standardization while enabling systematic cross-diary comparison. This also allowed for analysis and comparison of the *multilingual* corpus of texts.

This preliminary work brought several interesting insights, for instance, unveiling how the proportion between war- and everyday life-related words changed from early to later entries in diaries from three regions differently torn by war.

Figure 4. MaxDictio Frequency Analysis: War- and Life-Related Vocabulary Across Diaries from Three Ukrainian Regions.

Still, the primary outcome was methodological rather than empirical. This preliminary stage prevented me from unconsciously *imposing my own expectations*, categorizations, or vocabulary onto a *terminologically diverse and multilingual* corpus in which contextual nuance is essential. It also *sharpened my sensitivity* to the internal language of each diary and prepared me for the subsequent phase of close reading and thematic coding. Moreover, it offered a limited but meaningful avenue for *automation*: equipped with document-specific vocabularies, I was able to use search functions more effectively, both across and within documents. This exploratory step, though rough, thus served as a crucial bridge between raw text and interpretive analysis.

4. Example of findings and interpretations: Ambivalent normality

At this pilot stage, I kept the code system open and emergent, while still focused on my analytical research question: how do themes related to continuity of pre-war ‘normal life’ and the normalization of the previously abnormal co-occur and are experientially entangled within the same or nearby diary segments – not simply mentioned side by side, but narratively or reflectively intertwined.

To answer this question, I used three top-level codes to mark segments related to

Although preliminary and limited in scope, this pilot study revealed an intriguing patterns.

Continuation of the previous normality + Merging war and normal life. All diaries strongly emphasize the continuation of usual daily routines that remain unchanged compared to pre-war time. Authors describe how they bake cookies, clean the apartment, help children with their homework – although accompanied by sirens and explosions.

As soon as I sifted the flour and started kneading the dough, the siren went off. No sooner had it fallen silent than a loud explosion shattered the twilight silence outside the window. The bowl of dough fell from my hands onto the table. ‘Well, there go my dumplings!’ I thought. (Kari, Pos. 90)

Diaries depict daily city life that remains paradoxically normal – sometimes “*more normal*” than in “*normal*” times: the streets are kept clean, cafés that closed in the early days of war are reopening, new businesses arise, new buildings are being built, couples get married, children are born. Yet this normality is woven into fundamentally abnormal conditions.

In Kyiv, life goes on. We drink coffee. Work. Go to the gym. Celebrate birthdays. Cars drive through the city. New films premiere; new stores open. By day, everything almost feels normal. At night, the soundtrack of reality changes: booming of air defense, hum of drones, short messages in public chats: 'Are you safe? Is it close to you?' But the next morning, I still take children to school, drink my coffee, go to the gym. (Savenko, Pos. 14)

We say:

It's ok if we dance, sing, and drink coffee while our soldiers and civilians die, and cities are being destroyed. We must stay alive and be happy – this is what the enemy tries to take away from us. This is what we are fighting for.

Baking cookies, going to the gym, or cleaning the apartment during a war is not "coping" – it's a defiant act of preserving the aim of a full, human life.

And all this gradually gets habitual or at least livable. Explosions no longer interrupt a conversation but are absorbed into it. Office workers keep working after air alerts instead of running to the shelter. Transport companies do not reschedule itineraries. We buy new apartments in heavily shelled districts – the prices are lower. What once marked rupture becomes background. War becomes part of the city's rhythm – something we have learned to live with.

Ten days ago, Kharkiv experienced the most intense shelling of this war. Almost all of the strikes (40 drones, 4 aerial bombs and 2 rockets) were close to us, in one place. Two hours and 20 minutes of horror. Do you know what I did at 5:20, when the explosions stopped? I bought tickets online for a concert. (Roiz, Pos. 23)

It is more than just a continuation – it is a paradoxical condition in which **life not merely continues but often intensifies**. This does not come from ignoring war as a coping strategy, but from living fully in its presence, where the constant proximity of disruption sharpens the value of continuity.

We live life against the backdrop of death. We are closer to the abyss. (Savenko, Pos. 15)

Yet this is only one side of what is going on. Daily death reports, destroyed buildings, children got used to sleeping in bathrooms, and public lectures moved to basements – and how we all are gradually yet inevitably changing – all this suggests: things that once seemed **unthinkable gradually become part of everyday reality and, paradoxically, is normalized**.

In the early days, when burnt Russian tanks were brought to the walls of St. Michael's Cathedral, there was a distinct smell of 'burnt meat' hanging over the square. I have never considered myself a bloodthirsty person, but in my opinion, this exhibition would only benefit if burnt Russian tanks were complemented by a few members of their crews in the same condition, wouldn't it? At least, I wouldn't be disgusted and horrified by that brutal sight. So did my friend, who told that after an hour of smelling the odour of 'smoked Russians,' she and her husband went straight to 'Musafir' for a barbecue. (Kari, Pos. 535)

And of course, this habitualization does not mean erasure. Fear and sensitivity are suppressed, but the core experience of pain, mourn, and hatred does not disappear, but intensifies with every new attack. **The fundamental moral horizons preserve.** War is not reinterpreted as a normal or acceptable condition. The enemy is never redefined as a liberator. In this sense war never becomes “the new normal” as media and even scholarly papers tend to claim now. We remain humane, for example – to everyone except enemies.

My husband's colleague, Eugene, came over tonight to pick up bomb tails that had just been printed on the 3D-printer. His girlfriend Anna was with him. She went out onto the balcony and quickly ran inside, frightened by the nest the bumblebee had built there. "Why don't you get rid of it?" she asked. "Are you serious? Eugene exclaimed indignantly. "Have you just suggested depriving unborn bumblebees of their chance at life?" We exchanged smiles: this was said by a man whose work was to kill people, every day. (Rozanov, Pos. 1).

Neither do we adopt the idea of being “one people” being pushed by Russian propaganda.

When, in the morning silence of Sunday morning, the chirping of birds is interrupted by the roar of a rocket landing, you know for sure why you didn't like all those Pushkins, Bulgakovs, Tolstoys, Tchaikovskys, and Turgenevs! You know for sure: they are not 'ours,' absolutely not. (Kari, Pos. 546).

Taken together, these patterns reveal a recurring tripartite configuration of patterns I denoted as **ambivalent normality**. Across all diaries, three interrelated tendencies consistently appear: (i) the continuation and even intensification of everyday routines (*following normal routines, working, meeting friends, enjoying moments of life*), (ii) the gradual normalization of previously unthinkable things (*from sleeping under attacks, walking along ruins, or rejoice at killed human beings – although enemies*), and (iii) the preservation of fundamental moral reference points (*e.g. keeping national identity, refusing to give up, being humane towards animals*). This shows how the staying involves neither complete normalization nor complete resistance, but is complex ambivalent condition.

It helped me refine my concept of the Stayer by suggesting this ambivalent normality one of the characteristic features of the staying as a living condition. The Stayer, thus, does not fully internalize or normalize the disrupted condition. Certain aspects of the rupture inevitably

become habitualized – people learn to sleep through air raid sirens, navigate curfews, and even tolerate persistent violence. But this adaptation is superficial: the new order is neither accepted nor internalized. Pain, fear, and outrage do not vanish; moral boundaries are not redrawn. Those who embrace the changed order (*for instance, residents of occupied territories who believed they had been “liberated”*) as well as those who put it out of their minds and live as usual – cease to be Stayers. The disruption – in my case, war – is a constant, omnipresent shared background of the staying. It is never felt “normal” – even if it might look so from beyond – and the staying always remains a condition of collective estrangement within a disrupted homeworld.

5. Discussion

This report presents my first attempt of both design of my empirical study and interpreting results. I hope, when more work is done, its first part may become a backbone for a **methodological** paper, discussing challenges (and solutions) for those who work with complex, non-standardized, multilingual literary sources in MAXQDA – and broader, for everyone conducting qualitative analysis of such data. As the first step, I consider suggesting this paper for MAXQDA blog.

This pilot study may also lay ground for my subsequent interpretive, analytical, and even conceptual work. While it currently focuses solely on the boundaries of normality in wartime diaries, I expect a broad range of other characteristics of the Stayer experience to be identified. Describing and systematizing these features may allow for refining both empirical and theoretical boundaries of the Stayer concept.

Furthermore, in this pilot study, I do not analyse any technical codes (temporal and spatial), while already assigning them to the diaries in the study. I believe they will reveal their analytical potential as my work progresses. Probably, something like phenomenological periodization of the Stayer experience will arise.